

DIFFERENT SCALES OF CORTICAL ORGANIZATION ARE SELECTIVELY TARGETED DURING THE PROGRESSION TO ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE

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Previous studies have shown that the topological organization of the cerebral cortex is altered in Alzheimer's disease (AD). However, it remains unknown whether different levels of the cortical hierarchy are homogeneously affected during disease progression, and which of these levels are mostly involved in the breakdown of metabolic (functional) connectivity. To fulfill these goals, we acquired structural magnetic resonance images (MRI) and positron emission tomography (PET) with the radiotracer ¹⁸F-fludeoxyglucose (FDG) in 29 healthy old (HO) adults, 29 amnesic mild cognitive impairment (aMCI) and 29 mild AD patients. Structural and metabolic connections were obtained from inter-regional correlations of cortical thickness and glucose consumption, respectively. Results showed that AD and HO groups differed at all levels of cortical organization (i.e., whole cortex, hemisphere, lobe and node), whereas differences among the three groups were only evident at the lobe and node levels. The correlation between structural and metabolic connectivity (F-S coupling) was also disturbed during AD progression, affecting to different connectivity scales: it decreased at the local level, revealing a progressive increase of metabolic connections in those local communities with fewer structural connections; whereas it increased at the global level, likely due to a parallel reduction of cortical thickness and glucose consumption between long-distance cortical regions. Collectively, these results reveal that different levels of cortical organization are selectively affected during the transition from normal aging to dementia, which could be helpful to track cortical dysfunctions during AD progression.

Keywords: Cortical scales, Alzheimer's disease, mild cognitive impairment, structural connectivity, metabolic connectivity, functional-structural coupling.

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1. Introduction

Compelling data from many sources has revealed a continuum of neuropathologic findings and cognitive dysfunctions from normal aging to dementia, showing that cerebral lesions start to appear years, even decades, before the clinical onset of Alzheimer's disease (AD)¹. Accumulated evidence has further established the vulnerability of neocortex to AD lesions, not only in AD patients^{2,3} but also in cognitively normal elderly with high cerebral load of beta-amyloid (A β)^{4,5}, likely leading to connectivity failures that affect local cortical networks⁶⁻⁸ and large-scale cortical systems⁹⁻¹². Using functional neuroimaging techniques, such as functional MRI (fMRI), electro- and magnetoencephalography (EEG/MEG), recent studies have revealed that disruptions of functional connectivity patterns represent a potential biomarker for automated detection and diagnosis of AD¹³⁻¹⁹.

Cortical regions involved in integrative functions are the main targets of AD^{20,21}, these cortical hubs showing high A β deposition²⁰, larger atrophies^{22,23}, and marked functional deactivations²⁴. However, it remains to be explored how different levels of cortical organization (i.e., whole cortex, hemisphere, lobe and node) contribute to network changes during the transition from normal aging to AD, and whether this contribution affects similarly to structural and metabolic (functional) cortical networks. Additionally, local connections and modularity of the metabolic cortical network have shown to account for the coupling level between functional and structural networks (F-S coupling) in cognitively intact elderly subjects, suggesting that this relationship is mainly constrained by segregation properties of the metabolic network²⁵. Though it remains to be elucidated to what extent F-S coupling is affected in AD, whether F-S coupling undergoes changes during the course of AD, and which specific cortical elements account for these changes in F-S coupling during the transition from normal aging to AD.

It has been recently shown that AD patients have failures in long-distance functional connections that are paralleled by cognitive impairment²⁶. However, alterations in functional connectivity have been mostly based on hemodynamically-driven changes derived from fMRI, neglecting the tight association between glucose uptake and synaptic activity^{27,28} and/or synaptic density²⁹, both phenomena affected from early stages of

AD^{30,31}. Based on this evidence, failures in functional connectivity associated with AD progression may be better revealed by metabolic networks due to the established relationship between failures in metabolic connectivity and synaptic dysfunctions/loss associated with AD.

To shed light on these issues, here we have investigated to what extent the hierarchical organization of neocortex and F-S coupling levels are progressively affected during the transition to AD. More specifically, we have examined whether changes in cortical connectivity patterns occurring during the course of disease are accounted for by (i) global topological properties (ii) intra/inter hemispheric connectivity, (iii) inward and outward lobes connections and/or (iv) redistribution of hubs. Finally, we have assessed the relationship between connectivity strength and interregional distance, and whether the breakdown of connectivity associated with AD progression is related to reorganization of spatial attributes in cortical networks. To address these issues, we have analyzed structural and metabolic cortical networks derived from correlations of cortical thickness and regional glucose utilization in HO, aMCI subjects and mild AD patients.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Subjects

Eighty-seven participants (29 HO, 29 aMCI and 29 mild AD patients) were recruited for the study. Each subject received neurological, neuropsychological, MRI and FDG-PET assessments. Only those who met the established criteria (see below) were included in the study. All participants (or family members) gave their informed consent prior to their inclusion in the study, which was approved by the Ethical Committee for Human Research at Pablo de Olavide University.

aMCI subjects showed an idiopathic amnesic disorder with absence of impairment in cognitive domains other than memory, and they further met diagnostic criteria for aMCI³²: i) subjective memory complaints corroborated by the informant; ii) objective memory loss confirmed by the Spanish version of the Logical Memory subtest included in the Wechsler Memory Scale-Third Edition (scorings 1.5 standard deviations below the age-appropriate mean); iii) global score of 0.5

(questionable dementia) in the Clinical Dementia Rating (CDR)³³; iv) normal independence function, as revealed by the Interview for Deterioration in Daily Living Activities validated in the Spanish population³⁴; and v) no DSM-IV criteria for dementia. The global cognitive status was assessed with the Spanish version of the Mini Mental State Examination (MMSE)³⁵. Depression was excluded with the shorter version of the Geriatric Depression Scale³⁶. AD diagnosis was made according to the DSM-IV criteria. All AD patients were in the mild stage, corresponding to the stage IV of the Global Deterioration Scale³⁷ and confirmed by the Functional Assessment Staging³⁸. None of the participants were taking cholinesterase inhibitors, and/or psychiatric medication at the time of recruiting.

Inclusion criteria for HO subjects were (i) no subjective memory complaints or memory impairment corroborated by neuropsychological assessment, (ii) Clinical Dementia Rating (CDR) score of 0 (no dementia), and (iii) normal independent function. HO subjects were previously used in other study to establish F-S coupling patterns in normal aging²⁵.

2.2. MRI acquisition

Structural MR cerebral images were acquired on a whole-body Philips Achieva 3T scanner equipped with an 8-channel head coil. One high-resolution MP-RAGE (magnetization-prepared rapid gradient echo) T1-weighted anatomical sequence was obtained from each participant. Acquisition parameters were empirically optimized for grey/white contrast (0.8 mm³ isotropic voxel resolution, no gap between slices, TR = 11 ms, TE = 4.5 ms, flip angle = 8°, FOV = 256 x 256 x 160, acquisition time = 9.1 min).

Cortical thickness was estimated using surface-based methods with analysis tools implemented in Freesurfer v5.1 (<http://surfer.nmr.mgh.harvard.edu/>). Briefly, the cortical thickness analysis pipeline involves intensity normalization, registration to Talairach space, skull stripping, segmentation of white matter (WM), tessellation of the WM boundary, and automatic correction of topological defects. The tessellated surface is used for a deformable surface algorithm as the starting point to find the WM and then the pial boundary. For each vertex of the tessellated WM surface, the cortical thickness was calculated as the average of

the distance from the WM surface to the closest point on the pial surface, and from that point back to the closest point on the WM surface³⁹. Additionally, pial/WM boundaries were manually corrected on a slice-by-slice basis in each participant to increase the reliability of cortical thickness measurements. Special attention was paid to cortical regions at the border with cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) to avoid partial volume effects.

2.3. FDG-PET acquisition and pre-processing

FDG-PET cerebral images were acquired on a whole-body PET-TAC Siemens Biograph 16 HiREZ scanner (Siemens Medical Systems, Germany) with in-plane and axial resolution of 4.2 and 4.5 mm full-width at half maximum (FWHM), respectively. Subjects fasted for at least 8 h before the PET examination. Intravenous lines were placed 10-15 min before the tracer injection of a mean dose of 370 MBq of 2-[18F]fluoro-2-deoxy-D-glucose (FDG). PET scans lasted approximately 30 min. A transmission scan was used for attenuation correction, and FDG-PET cerebral images were reconstructed with 2.6 x 2.6 x 2 mm voxel resolution by using standard 2D back-projection filters. We applied partial volume correction (PVC) to cerebral FDG-PET cerebral images using the algorithm implemented in the PMOD software v3.17 (<http://www.pmod.com>)⁴⁰. Absolute values of PVC-FDG cerebral consumption were normalized to the mean cerebellar glucose utilization in the native brain space of each participant.

2.4. Cortical parcellation

Previous studies have shown that different parcellation schemes have a strong impact on the topology of diffusion-based structural brain networks⁴¹, as well as on fMRI-based functional connectivity⁴². To overcome this issue, we have employed a cortical scheme comprising 641 regions (250 mm² each) that has shown a good trade-off between small-world attributes and the number of cortical regions in morphometric networks⁴³. Furthermore, using a common parcellation scheme for structural and metabolic networks allows comparison of topological properties between both networks as well as determining group differences from normal aging to AD.

2.5. Construction of cortical networks

Structural and metabolic cortical networks were built from partial correlations of interregional cortical thickness and cortical glucose values, respectively. Effects of age, gender, and age-gender interaction were previously removed for each group separately by applying a linear regression analysis across cortical regions⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶.

Cortical networks are commonly inferred from neuroimaging datasets integrated by fewer subjects than cortical regions^{47,48}. This scenario, known as “small n , large p ”, leads to overfitted statistical models with high variability and low generalization capability⁴⁹. To partially solve this problem, a shrinkage-based regularization method was applied to obtain a well-conditioned and positive-definite covariance matrix in each group⁵⁰. Finally, partial correlations between region i and j (r_{ij}) was derived from the corrected covariance matrix as:

$$r_{ij} = -S_{ij}^{-1} / \sqrt{S_{ii}^{-1} \times S_{jj}^{-1}} \quad (1)$$

where S_{ij}^{-1} represents the $\{i,j\}$ th element of the inverted covariance matrix S^{-1} computed from all possible pairs of cortical regions.

Student t -test cannot be applied to experimental designs constrained by the “small n , large p ” problem since they have statistical distributions with negative degrees of freedom. To overcome this limitation, Monte Carlo permutation tests were used to estimate a distribution derived from pooling regional pairwise partial correlations resulting in 1,640,960 permuted r -values. The 95th percentile of this distribution was used as significance threshold to reject the null hypothesis that correlation between regions occurred by chance. False positives were controlled for structural and metabolic networks separately using the false discovery rate (FDR) approach (q -value < 0.05)⁵¹.

Structural and metabolic connectivity was modeled through weighted graphs to encode the strength of the connections between cortical regions. For group comparisons, each of the six partial correlation matrices (2 cortical networks \times 3 groups of participants) was transformed into a weight connectivity matrix using a linear normalization:

$$w_{ij} = \frac{r_{ij} - \min[r_{p<0.05}]}{\max[r] - \min[r_{p<0.05}]} \quad (2)$$

where $\{w_{ij}\} \in [0,1]$ represents the connection strength between node i and node j , r_{ij} is the partial correlation value between region i and j , $\max[r]$ is the maximum value of partial correlation, and $\min[r_{p<0.05}]$ is the minimum correlation value above the statistical threshold (corrected p -value < 0.05) obtained in each experimental condition. Correlations below the statistical threshold were considered unconnected ($w_{ij} = 0$), whereas values between 0 and 1 were assigned to the rest of significant connections.

2.6. Assessing topological properties of cortical networks

Many real complex networks exhibit small world properties characterized by a high clustering and local efficiency (i.e., segregation), as well as short average distance between any two nodes (i.e., integration)⁵². The *weighted clustering coefficient* of the network ($C_p \in [0,1]$) was computed as the likelihood whether the neighboring nodes of any network node are connected amongst each other⁵³:

$$C_p = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j,k \in G} \frac{(w_{ij}w_{jk}w_{ik})^{1/3}}{(k_i(k_i-1)/2)} \quad (3)$$

where N is the number of regions, w_{ij} is the weight connection between region i and j , and k_i is the degree of node i .

Weighted characteristic path length was defined as the average minimum travel distance that link any two nodes of the network, considered as the inverse of the weights of the connections⁵⁴:

$$L_p = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{N(N-1)} \sum_{i,j} \left(\frac{1}{L_{ij}}\right)} \quad (4)$$

where L_{ij} is the inverse of the edge weight ($L_{ij} = 1/w_{ij}$).

The wiring length reveals the metabolic and material cost of network configuration. This integration index was quantified with the *outreach* metric (O_p), denoting the network ability to establish significant connections between distant cortical regions:

$$O_p = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{ij} w_{ij} d_{ij} \quad (5)$$

where N is the number of regions, w_{ij} is the weight connection between region i and j , and d_{ij} is the Euclidean distance between centroids of region i and j .

To investigate group differences in lobe connectivity, we computed the *inward/outward lobe connection strength* (S_l) in frontal, central, parietal, temporal, occipital and limbic (integrated by the cingulate cortex) lobes:

$$S_l = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{ij} w_{ij} \quad (6)$$

where S_l is the sum of weights of the lobe (l) separated into four categories: (i) S_l^{in} reveals connections between regions that belongs to l , (ii) S_l^{intraH} shows connections from l to nodes out of l with the endpoint in the same hemisphere, (iii) S_l^{interH} refers to connections from l that cross to the opposite hemisphere, and (iv) $S_l^{in/out} = S_l^{in} / (S_l^{intraH} + S_l^{interH})$ shows the preference of l for inward connectivity opposed to connections that leave l . In all cases, the strength of lobe connectivity was averaged across the two cortical hemispheres. The inward/outward strength of the whole cortical network (represented as S_p) was computed as the average S_l of the six cortical lobes ($S_p^{in/out} = \sum_l S_l^{in/out} / 6$). The *intra-hemispheric proportion* (IH_p) index was defined as the ratio of connections within a hemisphere to connections that cross to the contralateral hemisphere:

$$IH_p = \frac{\sum_{intra(i,j)} w_{ij}}{\sum_{inter(i,j)} w_{ij}} \quad (7)$$

where $intra(i,j)$ has a value of 1 if regions i and j are located in the same hemisphere, and 0 if the two regions are located in different hemispheres. On the contrary, 1 in $inter(i,j)$ means that regions i and j belong to different hemispheres, and 0 that they are located in the same hemisphere.

The above metrics may be influenced by characteristics of the network structure, such as the number of nodes and the amount of weights within the graph, making comparisons across modalities and groups problematic. To counteract these effects, 100 random networks with similar properties to the real network were built permuting all the network weights in each group⁵⁵. This process preserves the nodes and the sum of weights but not the degree distribution. Finally, each metric (C_p , L_p ,

O_p , S_{tp} and IH_p) was normalized by dividing the real value by the average across the 100 randomly rewired networks. A normalized metric value (C_p^w , L_p^w , O_p^w , IH_p^w or $S_p^{in/out}$) higher than 1 indicates that the measured characteristic is over represented in the real network compared with the null model.

2.7. Assessing the effect of distance on connectivity strength

To determine whether changes in the association between cortical connectivity and distance parallel AD progression, we computed the distribution of significant partial correlations as a function of the interregional distance in intervals of 20 mm. The Euclidean distance between centroids of two nodes was calculated considering the mean Talairach coordinates of voxels comprising each node⁵⁶.

We further investigated group differences in patterns of inter-hemispheric connectivity between homologous cortical regions. In this case, the distribution of significant partial correlation was assessed as a function of the distance between contralateral homologous regions. Inter-hemispheric distances were computed assuming anatomical connections through callosal fibers:

$$interDist(x,y) = \|x - CC\|_2 + \|y - CC\|_2 \quad (8)$$

where $InterDist(x,y)$ refers to the inter-hemispheric distance between one region located in the x coordinate of the left hemisphere and other region located in the y coordinate of the right hemisphere, whereas CC corresponds to coordinates of the centroid of the corpus callosum and $\|\cdot\|_2$ denotes the L_2 -norm (i.e., the Euclidean norm). This definition of distance for regions located in opposed hemispheres contributed to partially correct the Euclidean underestimation of inter-hemispheric pathways.

2.8. Estimation of node centrality and network modularity

Hubs can be classified into local or global according to whether they preferentially incorporate short-range or long-range connections, respectively. In the present work, local hubs were defined as highly connected cortical regions (mean + 1.5 SD) within 30 mm of a

neighborhood area, whereas global hubs were cortical regions highly connected (mean + 1.5 SD) with regions separated by more than 30 mm. The local/global boundary of 30 mm was selected on the basis of the maximum length of the intracortical U-fibers⁵⁷. Consequently, local hubs were integrated by structural connections determined by the U-fiber system whereas global hubs mainly contain cortico-cortical long-range connections.

Highly interconnected regions shape network communities with a modular organization⁵⁸. To assess the presence of non-overlapped modules in each group, the modularity of each node (Q_i) was computed according to the Leicht and Newman's algorithm⁵⁴:

$$Q_i = \frac{1}{w_{net}} \sum_j [w_{ij} - \frac{w_i w_j}{w_{net}}] \delta(c_i, c_j) \quad (9)$$

where w_{net} is the sum of all network weights, $\delta(c_i, c_j)$ is the Kronecker delta, and c_i and c_j the communities of nodes i and j , respectively. Nodes with Q_i above the mean plus 1.5 times the standard deviation were classified as modular. Considering the modular partition, we assigned a specific role to each cortical region accordingly with their preference for intra-modular or inter-modular connections. The participation coefficient of a given node was defined as the proportion of edges linking it to nodes in other modules:

$$P_i = 1 - \sum_{s=1}^{N_M} \left(\frac{k_{c_i}}{k_i} \right)^2 \quad (10)$$

where N_M is the number of identified modules, k_i refers to the degree of the node i , and k_{c_i} to the number of edges from the i^{th} node to nodes within module c_i . Consequently, nodes with a large number of intra-modular connections were referred as *provincial* (p_i lower than the average), whereas those nodes with a substantial proportion of inter-modular edges were referred as *connector* (p_i higher than the average). Modules and hubs of each group (HO, aMCI, AD) were represented over cortical surface maps with the BrainNet Viewer (<http://www.nitrc.org/projects/bnv/>).

2.9. Measuring levels of functional-structural (F-S) coupling in cortical networks

Using a method to predict fMRI connectivity from diffusion-based structural networks⁵⁶, coupling between metabolic (functional) and structural cortical networks (F-S coupling) was determined as the Pearson's correlation between the partial correlation matrix of cortical thickness (structural connectivity) and the partial correlation matrix of cortical glucose utilization (metabolic connectivity)⁵⁶. Based on previous evidence²⁵, we hypothesize that each type of node and connection contributes differently to the level of F-S coupling in each group of participants. To assess this hypothesis, we have distinguished between local (correlations between regions closer than 30 mm) and global F-S coupling (correlations between regions separated by more than 30 mm). Furthermore, local/global F-S coupling was also restricted to nodal characteristics, differentiating between (i) all nodes (ii) nodes with high degree (hubs), and (iii) nodes with high modularity. As F-S coupling is highly affected by the network modality used as a predictor^{25,56,59}, F-S coupling was evaluated for the structural and metabolic network elements on separate analyses.

2.10. Statistical analyses

We first assessed the normality assumption of data distribution with the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. All demographics and cognitive values were normally distributed, allowing us to use parametric statistical tests. Group differences in demographic and cognitive variables were assessed with one-way ANOVA, whereas differences in gender were tested with the chi-square test due to the categorical nature of this variable. All these analyses were performed with SPSS v.15 (SPSS Inc. Chicago, IL).

As the distribution of the different network metrics is unknown, we applied nonparametric permutation tests to assess group differences for each metric (global topological properties, relationship between connectivity and distance, nodal centrality, and F-S coupling). Briefly, for each network modality (structural and metabolic) and for each pair of groups (HO vs MCI, HO vs AD, MCI vs AD), each subject was randomly reallocated to one of the two groups. Based on the randomly resampled subjects, connectivity matrices and networks metrics were calculated using the same procedure as with the original data. Differences between metrics for each pairwise combination of permutations

(11175 permutations in total) were computed to build a reference distribution. Finally, the 95th percentile value of the distribution was used as statistical threshold to retain or reject the null hypothesis of no group difference in a specific metric. Comparison of connectivity strength across a wide-ranging of distances (from 20 mm to 200 mm in steps of 20 mm) led to 10 statistical inferences simultaneously. This multiple testing issue was counteracted employing a unique reference distribution collecting, for each subject permutation, the maximum metric difference in the 10 cases. The 95th percentile of the 11175 maximum values of differences represents a more restrictive threshold, which was used to control the family-wise error (FWE) rate⁶⁰.

3. Results

3.1. Demographics and cognitive profile

Table 1 shows demographic and cognitive characteristics for each group. Groups significantly differed in age ($F_{2,84} = 5.2$; $p = 0.007$), being AD patients older than HO subjects ($p = 0.007$). As expected, significant group differences arose in cognition: MMSE ($F_{2,84} = 47.1$; $p = 10^{-5}$); immediate ($F_{2,84} = 43.6$; $p = 10^{-6}$) and delayed ($F_{2,84} = 108.8$; $p = 10^{-6}$) memory. In general, cognitive functioning was more impaired in AD patients than in the other groups ($10^{-6} < p < 10^{-5}$), and aMCI subjects showed intermediate values between HO and AD ($10^{-6} < p < 0.03$).

3.2. Topological properties of cortical networks

Figure 1 displays topological properties of structural (Figure 1A) and metabolic (Figure 1B) cortical networks in HO, aMCI and AD patients. Segregation capability (C_p) was significantly increased in AD patients compared to HO in both structural (AD > HO, $p < 0.02$) and metabolic (AD > HO, $p < 0.002$) networks, together with significant deficits in network integration. The latter effect, confirmed by the O_p) metric, was derived from the lower capacity of AD patients to reach distant nodes in the structural (HO > AD, $p < 0.04$) and metabolic (HO > AD, $p < 10^{-6}$; aMCI > AD, $p < 0.04$) cortical network. The lack of group differences in path

length (L_p) reveals that this metric is not as sensible as O_p to detect subtle differences in network integration. We further found that intra-hemispheric connections prevailed over inter-hemispheric connections (IH_p) in both structural (AD > HO, $p < 0.03$) and metabolic networks (AD > HO, $p < 10^{-6}$; aMCI > HO, $p < 0.0007$), result that was extended to cortical lobes. Particularly, results showed that the inward/outward lobe connectivity ratio ($S_p^{in/out}$) progressively increased from HO to aMCI (aMCI > HO, $p < 0.04$), and from aMCI to AD (AD > aMCI, $p < 10^{-6}$), the difference between HO and AD being the largest (AD > HO, $p < 10^{-6}$). Interestingly, the lobular segregation shown by aMCI and AD patients only reached significance in the metabolic network. Overall, these results confirm an enhancement of segregation and impairment of integration at different network levels (i.e., whole network, hemispheres and cortical lobes) with AD progression. This cortical reorganization affected similarly to structural and metabolic networks, although differences between aMCI and the two other groups were mostly restricted to metabolic networks.

Table 1. Demographic and clinical characteristics of the study cohort

	HO (N=29)	aMCI (N=29)	AD (N=29)
Age (years)	66.6 ± 5	70.2 ± 6.6	71.8 ± 7 ^{b*}
Gender (M/F)	13 / 16	19 / 10	14 / 15
Education level (yrs)	7.3 ± 4.2	6.9 ± 5.4	6.3 ± 4.3
CDR	0	0.5	1
MMSE	28.4 ± 1.3	26.9 ± 2.4 ^{c***}	22 ± 3.6 ^{b***}
Immediate memory	14.1 ± 3 ^{***}	9.0 ± 2.6 ^{c*}	7.0 ± 3.3 ^{b***}
Delayed memory	13.1 ± 2.7 ^{***}	5.6 ± 3.3 ^{c***}	1.3 ± 3.1 ^{b***}

Results are expressed as mean ± standard deviation, except for gender and CDR. M/F male/female; CDR, Clinical Dementia Rating, 0 = lack of dementia, 0.5 = questionable dementia, 1 = mild dementia; MMSE, Mini Mental State Examination. ^a HO > aMCI; ^b HO > AD; ^c aMCI > AD. * $p < 0,05$; ** $p < 10^{-5}$

Figure 1. Group differences in topological properties of structural (A) and metabolic (B) networks. The clustering coefficient (C_p^w) is a metric of local efficiency (segregation); both the path length (L_p^w) and outreach (O_p^w) metrics account for network integration; whereas the intra/interhemispheric connectivity (IH_p^w) and inward/outward lobe connectivity metrics ($S_p^{in/out}$) refer to the ratio between network segregation and integration. Asterisks indicate significant group differences in each metric ($p < 0.05$, corrected for multiple comparisons).

3.3. Functional-structural (F-S) coupling in cortical networks

Figure 2 displays group differences in levels of F-S coupling predicted by the connections and nodal attributes of the structural (Figure 2A) and metabolic cortical network (Figure 2B), computed for different spatial scales (local/global) and different network attributes (all nodes, hubs and modules). Global connections showed an increased F-S coupling with AD progression for structural (AD > HO, $p < 0.03$; AD > aMCI, $p < 0.004$) and functional (AD > HO, $p < 0.01$) network elements. The same result was shown for global connections of the modular nodes (structural: AD > HO, $p < 0.03$; metabolic: AD > HO, $p < 0.03$). Local connections of hubs and modules revealed an opposite trend that only reached significance when F-S coupling was predicted from metabolic connections (local hubs: HO > AD, $p < 0.02$; local modules: HO > AD, $p < 0.03$). In summary, AD patients, contrary to aMCI, showed changes in F-S coupling that affected oppositely to local and global connectivity patterns, resulting in local F-S decoupling and increased global F-S coupling respectively. In particular, abnormal coupling behavior

became more evident in cortical hubs and modules, confirming the higher vulnerability of these regions to AD lesions^{20,21}.

3.4. Intra- and inter-hemispheric connection lengths

Figure 3 illustrates group differences in lengths of intra-hemispheric (upper panels) and inter-hemispheric (lower panels) connections for structural and metabolic cortical networks. These analyses revealed that short-distance intra-hemispheric metabolic connections were more predominant in aMCI/AD patients than in HO subjects (0-40 mm: aMCI > HO, $p < 10^{-3}$; AD > HO, $p < 10^{-6}$, corrected for multiple comparisons). The same result was obtained for short-distance inter-hemispheric metabolic connections (0-40 mm: aMCI > HO, $p < 0.01$; AD > HO, $p < 0.001$, corrected for multiple comparisons). On the contrary, aMCI and AD showed a lower proportion of long-distance metabolic connections at the intra-hemispheric (100 mm: HO > AD, $p < 0.002$; HO > aMCI, $p < 10^{-3}$, corrected for multiple comparisons) and inter-hemispheric level (80 mm: HO > AD, $p < 0.004$; 100-120 mm: HO > AD, $p < 0.02$, corrected for multiple comparisons). The distribution of intra- and inter-hemispheric connection

Figure 2. Group differences in levels of functional-structural (F-S) connectivity coupling. **(A)** The presence of metabolic (functional) connections was inferred from structural connections. **(B)** The presence of structural connections was inferred from metabolic (functional) connections. Each column represents local (short-range connections; within 30 mm) and global (long-range connections; farther than 30 mm) coupling for different network attributes (whole network, hubs and modules). Asterisks indicate significant group differences in each modality of F-S coupling ($p < 0.05$, corrected for multiple comparisons).

Figure 3. Structural and metabolic distribution of connections with different lengths. Plots illustrate the distribution of intra-hemispheric (upper row) and inter-hemispheric connections (bottom row) in the structural and metabolic network for each group (HO, aMCI, AD). Asterisks indicate significant group differences ($p < 0.05$, corrected for multiple comparisons).

lengths in the structural network was unaffected by AD progression. Overall, these results suggest that functional reorganization of the cerebral cortex is characterized by a profound reorganization of intra- and inter-hemispheric metabolic connections during the progression of AD, leading to increased local interactions at the expense of long-range connections.

3.5. Patterns of lobe connectivity

To determine if specific patterns of lobe connectivity were associated with different AD stages, we assessed group differences in connectivity of different cortical lobes (frontal, central, parietal, temporal, occipital and limbic) (Figure 4). aMCI and AD patients showed enhanced intra-lobe connectivity (S^{in}), although this phenomenon was not extended to all cortical lobes. Thus, AD patients showed stronger structural connections in the occipital lobe than aMCI subjects ($p < 0.04$). The same can be said of the metabolic connectivity within the central lobe (AD > aMCI, $p < 10^{-6}$). However, all groups were significantly distinguished on the basis of connectivity patterns within the limbic and temporal lobes. Thus, AD patients showed higher metabolic connectivity compared to HO within the limbic (AD > HO, $p < 10^{-6}$) and temporal lobe (AD > HO, $p < 10^{-6}$), whereas differences between HO and aMCI were only evident in the temporal lobe (aMCI > HO, $p < 0.005$), and differences between aMCI and AD were restricted to the limbic lobe (AD > aMCI, $p < 10^{-6}$). Similar results were observed when the analysis was extended to the connectivity pattern shown by each lobe within the same hemisphere (S^{intraH}). Again, structural connections with the occipital lobe ($p < 0.01$) and metabolic connections with the central lobe ($p < 10^{-16}$) were significantly increased in AD compared to aMCI individuals. Interestingly, the opposite pattern of results was revealed by the frontal and parietal lobes. The former showing a decrease of intra-hemispheric connections in AD patients compared to aMCI ($p < 0.002$), and the latter revealing a decrease of intra-hemispheric connections that distinguished AD patients (HO > AD, $p < 10^{-6}$) and aMCI (HO > aMCI, $p < 0.04$) from HO subjects. A consistent result was the decreased level of connectivity between one lobe with the other lobes in the contralateral hemisphere (S^{interH}) from AD to HO. This finding was evident for the structural connections in the frontal (HO > AD, $p < 0.02$; aMCI > AD, $p < 10^{-6}$) and temporal lobe (HO > AD, $p < 10^{-3}$;

aMCI > AD, $p < 0.035$), and for the metabolic connections in frontal (aMCI > AD, $p < 0.03$) and parietal lobes (HO > AD, $p < 10^{-6}$; aMCI > AD, $p < 0.014$). In the parietal lobe, aMCI and AD patients showed decreased connectivity when compared to HO subjects (HO > aMCI, $p < 0.001$). The opposite was found for structural inter-hemispheric connections to the central lobe (AD > HO, $p < 10^{-3}$; AD > aMCI, $p < 0.03$) and for metabolic connections to the limbic lobe (AD > HO, $p < 10^{-6}$; AD > aMCI, $p < 10^{-6}$).

Finally, we have evaluated the preference shown by each cortical lobe for establishing connections within the lobe (favoring lobe segregation) with respect to the preference for establishing connections with other lobes (promoting lobe integration), as revealed by the metric ($S_l^{in/out}$). AD patients showed a significant increase of intra-lobular connections in detriment of inter-lobular connections when compared to HO subjects, which was evident in the temporal (AD > HO, $p < 0.01$) and parietal lobe (AD > HO, $p < 0.003$) of the structural network. The same was found for the metabolic network when compared AD with aMCI patients, although in this particular case, significant differences were restricted to the frontal (AD > aMCI, $p < 0.03$), limbic (AD > aMCI, $p < 0.02$) and central lobes (AD > aMCI, $p < 0.02$). The ratio of intra- and inter-lobular connections further allowed distinguishing aMCI from HO subjects, in the temporal (aMCI > HO, $p < 0.001$), parietal (aMCI > HO, $p < 0.002$) and occipital lobes (aMCI > HO, $p < 0.02$).

3.6. Reorganization of global cortical hubs

Figure 5 shows group differences in the spatial distribution of global hubs in structural (Figure 5A) and metabolic cortical networks (Figure 5B) for each hemisphere (left, upper row; right, bottom row). Briefly, hubs were divided into those with high intra-modular connectivity (provincial hubs, represented as small spheres) and those with high inter-modular connectivity (connector hubs, represented as large spheres). Colors represent different sets of group comparisons. Tables 2 and 3 show topographic group differences for connector and provincial hubs in the structural and metabolic network, including the anatomical locations of these changes.

In HO subjects, structural connector hubs were predominantly located in the left lateral temporal cortex,

Figure 4. Group differences in the structural and metabolic connectivity at the lobe level. For each metric, only those lobes showing significant group differences are displayed. Each colour refers to a particular lobe: frontal (F, red), central (C, yellow), temporal (T, green), limbic (L, purple), parietal (P, blue) and occipital (O, brown). The intensity of the colour refers to a particular group (HO, aMCI and AD). Metrics of lobe connectivity included inward connectivity (S_i^{in}), connections towards the same (S_i^{intraH}) and the contralateral (S_i^{interH}) hemisphere, and the ratio between inward and outward connectivity ($S_i^{in/out}$).

right prefrontal cortex, and in heteromodal regions of the parietal and occipital lobes of both hemispheres (Figure 5A, left column). In the aMCI group, an increased proportion of structural hubs overlapped with frontal regions bilaterally, in more anterior regions when compared with HO subjects and in more posterior regions when compared with AD patients (Figure 5A, middle column). On the contrary, AD patients revealed a lack of global hubs over heteromodal associative areas of the temporal, parietal and prefrontal cortices, with the exception of two bilateral hubs located in the ventrolateral prefrontal cortex. Instead, they showed an increase of global hubs over central areas compared to both HO and aMCI individuals (Figure 5A, right column). Whereas HO and aMCI subjects showed a similar hub distribution in the metabolic network (Figure 5B), in AD patients was markedly different. Compared with results derived from the structural network, HO subjects showed a lack of metabolic

connector hubs in the frontal lobe together with an increase of these hubs in unimodal associative areas. aMCI subjects revealed an increase of metabolic connector hubs in posterior regions of the frontal lobe with respect to the higher amount of structural hubs in more anterior regions; as well as an increase of metabolic connector and provincial hubs in the ventral visual pathway, mainly restricted to the right hemisphere. Finally, network differences in AD patients revealed an increase of connector and provincial hubs in the temporal lobe of the two hemispheres that was extended to the prefrontal cortex. Overall, these analyses showed that heteromodal association areas diminished their role as pivotal regions in both aMCI and AD groups, shifting the nodal centrality toward less impaired cortical territories, as the somatosensory cortex.

4. Discussion

Figure 5. Group differences in the topographic distribution of global hubs in structural (A) and metabolic (B) networks. Smaller spheres represent regions with a large amount of intramodular connections (provincial hubs), whereas larger spheres show regions with a high concentration of intermodular connections (connector hubs). The colour of spheres indicates the direction of significant differences between pairs of groups. L = Left, R= Right

Precise and fast communication in cerebral cortex is governed by a wiring principle that balances the conservation of cellular material (spatial cost) and conduction delay (temporal cost)^{61,62}. The disruption of this balance may lead to synaptic dysfunctions and reduced efficiency of cortical networks in AD patients^{63,64}. Our findings extend this hypothesis to individuals with aMCI, and show that boundaries

between normal and pathological aging appear to be substantially dependent on the spatial scale of cortical connectivity. Thus, while network descriptors studied over the whole cortex clearly distinguished AD patients from HO, differences between aMCI and HO subjects only emerged at the hemispheric level. At the lobe level, each group differed from each other, at least in the metabolic network. Even at the node level, it was possible to identify a different spatial distribution of connector hubs in each group. These results suggest that different levels of cortical organization are selectively affected during the transition from normal aging to dementia, which could be helpful to track cortical dysfunctions during AD progression.

4.1. The interplay between cortical segregation/integration occurs at different connectivity scales during the progression to AD

By assessing network topology at different levels of cortical organization, we have shown increased network segregation in both aMCI individuals and AD patients. However, whereas differences between AD patients and HO subjects were extended to all cortical scales, in aMCI subjects they were only evident at the hemispheric level. These findings suggest that the spatial scale of cortical connectivity is critical to identify network abnormalities associated with AD progression. Regarding network integration, conclusions are tightly related to the metric employed. Thus, the capacity of integration did not change among groups when the path length (λ_g) metric was used, whereas the outreach metric (O_p^w), a network descriptor of long-range communication, was significantly diminished with AD progression.

Most of the resting-state studies performed in AD patients have based the functional connectivity patterns on correlations of fMRI time series^{26,65–68} or coherence/phase synchronization of EEG signal^{69–72}. To our knowledge, only two studies to date have evaluated

the evolution of cortical topology during AD progression using FDG-PET correlations^{73,74}. Different lines of evidence support that metabolic networks are particularly suitable to detect synaptic failures associated with AD^{75,76}. Firstly, and in agreement with the view of glucose utilization in the brain, once glutamate is released by active neurons, astrocytes metabolize glucose to lactate, which is then taken up by nearby neurons to sustain their energy demands⁷⁷. From this perspective, the FDG-PET signal could be considered as an indirect index of activation of neuronal circuits⁷⁸. Secondly, large amounts of A β have been detected in activated astrocytes of human AD brains⁷⁹, which due to their capacity to accumulate A β might change their metabolic function and become a diffusible factor of neurotoxicity⁸⁰. Finally, evidence has shown that regional cerebral glucose utilization measured by FDG-PET is related to the levels of synaptophysin, an indicator of synaptic density²⁹.

4.2. The relationship between structural and metabolic network connectivity is altered in AD

In agreement with previous results⁸¹, we showed a reduced relationship between structural and metabolic network connectivity in AD patients compared with both HO and aMCI subjects. Two important differences arise between the study of Ref. ⁸¹ and ours. Firstly, the decreased network coupling found in our study was restricted to local connections. When long-range connections were considered, AD patients showed the opposite trend, namely, an increased strength of F-S coupling. Secondly, the decreased network coupling at the local level was only evident when the presence of structural connectivity was inferred from metabolic connectivity, whereas the increased F-S coupling at global level was evident when the presence of metabolic interactions was inferred from structural connections.

Abnormally enhanced F-S connectivity coupling in the AD group could be driven by a combination of the generalized cortical atrophy⁸² and metabolic deficits⁸³. Thus, previous studies have shown that cortical thinning of frontal, parietal and temporal lobes is tightly related to the severity of symptoms in very mild and mild AD dementia⁸⁴. Moreover, these regions also show a generalized reduction of glucose, oxygen consumption, and cerebral blood flow⁸⁵.

4.3. Lengths of metabolic connections change with AD progression

Our study has revealed a profound rearrangement of metabolic connections with AD progression, involving an increase of local (20-40 mm) at the expense of long-distance connections (80-120 mm). Recent studies have shown that long-range functional connections in AD patients are specifically decreased in the range of 100-140 mm^{26,86}, the most affected being those located in the posterior cingulate cortex, precuneus and medial prefrontal cortex⁸⁶. Thus, the reduction of long-range connections was paralleled by increased short-range functional connections in the left fusiform gyrus and the left intraparietal cortex⁸⁶, and further correlated with AD severity based on MMSE scores²⁶. All together, these results suggest that the diminution of functional long-range connections is related to the loss of functional integrity of cortical networks associated with the cognitive decline in AD patients.

The present work has further shown that functional rearrangement associated with AD progression also affects both intra- and inter-hemispheric cortical connections. However, the decrease of inter-hemispheric connections was evident at longer distances in aMCI individuals and at relatively shorter distances in AD patients, which might result from different degrees of axonal degeneration in different bundles of the corpus callosum⁸⁷. In AD patients, these changes might result from the callosal degeneration of anterior and posterior regions⁸⁷⁻⁹¹, whereas in aMCI subjects the damage could be more restricted to early-myelinating posterior regions of the corpus callosum that communicate parietal and temporal subregions, areas that showed an increased isolation in the present study.

4.4. The topography of cortical hubs changes with AD progression

Evidence suggests that cortical regions with topological centrality (i.e., hubs) are more vulnerable to brain insults²¹. In AD patients, regions involved in the integration of anterior-posterior networks and those with a large density of inter-hemispheric connections have revealed to be particularly vulnerable to disease (for a review, see Ref. ⁹²). In agreement with these results, the posterior cingulate and precuneus usually show higher A β concentration, lower glucose metabolism, and larger atrophies in aMCI and AD patients⁹³⁻⁹⁶. These findings

are coherent with the relationship between the node degree and the regional load of A β ²⁰.

However, the distribution of connector hubs in the prefrontal cortex showed a quite selective pattern in aMCI, indicating that dementia could be a discrete categorical entity⁹⁷. From this perspective, dementia results from neurological deficits and, thus, is viewed as a state qualitatively different from normal cognitive aging⁹⁸. In line with this hypothesis, aMCI showed a lateralized increase in the number of structural and metabolic connector hubs in lateral regions of the left prefrontal cortex when compared to both HO and AD patients (Figure 5B). This abnormal pattern of connectivity might result from the high A β load accumulated in these regions during the course of disease^{99,100}. Accordingly, previous studies have reported increased levels of resting-state EEG functional connectivity in aMCI subjects^{101,102}, likely revealing synaptic failures derived from the vulnerability of pyramidal neurons to the accumulation of A β aggregates. Alternatively, the increased number of connector hubs revealed by aMCI individuals might denote the activation of a compensatory mechanism^{103,104}. Increase in lateralization of frontal hubs in both modalities is consistent with previous studies that have reported that AD induces stronger amyloid deposition and grey matter atrophy in the frontal lobe of the left hemisphere^{105,106}. Nonetheless, laterality could also reflect a recruitment bias since patients with more severe language dysfunctions have associated higher left hemispheric atrophy.

4.5. Limitations

There are a number of limitations in this study. First, AD subjects were significantly older than HO (Table 1). This difference can be particularly problematic due to aging has an strong impact on brain structural and functional topology^{107,108}. Thus, although a general linear model was applied to remove age effects, current results could partially reflect age-related topological disruption instead of being a consequence of disease progression. However, we also showed significant topological differences between groups with similar age (i.e., HO-aMCI and aMCI-AD), suggesting that the neurodegenerative process disrupts brain topology beyond the aging effect.

Second, compared with fMRI, PET studies have lower temporal and spatial resolution. In order to increase the signal-to-noise ratio, glucose consumption was averaged across time course and across vertices comprising each cortical region. Characterization of metabolic networks is particularly relevant in AD due to glucose uptake is strongly impaired by β -amyloid deposition¹⁰⁹. Nonetheless, global mean glucose uptake is highly influenced by the generalized cortical atrophy that characterize AD and by the amount of radiocontrast agent injected. In the current study, the normalization of the regional glucose uptake by the cerebellum consumption in each subject partially overcame this confounding factor, and has further demonstrated to improve the identification of dementia patients¹¹⁰.

Third, neuroanatomical interpretation of structural connections based on correlations of interregional cortical thickness is still under debate. Structural networks represent a subsampled and coarse-graining version of the underlying real human connectome and synaptome. Consequently, anatomical correspondence of structural connections (or co-variations) has been only partially validated using diffusion MRI¹¹¹. Traditional univariate methods (e.g. voxel-based morphometry) have focused on localising regional morphological abnormalities, providing a comprehensive view of atrophy patterns during healthy ageing¹¹² and pathological processes¹¹³. Complementary, multivariate approaches like structural networks conceptualizes the brain as a whole network, extracting information about high-level topology that is critical to understand how higher-order functions emerge from the interactions between brain areas^{114,115}. Notwithstanding, future studies will be necessary to provide better mechanistic comprehension of the relation between brain network architecture and microscopic cellular processes in order to discriminate between the contributing factors of a pathological condition and the ultimate consequences of the disease.

5. Conclusions

This study has shown that the transition from healthy aging to dementia is associated with more segregated and less efficient cortical networks. Impaired long-range functional connectivity accompanying AD progression seems to be driven by hemispheric and lobe isolation as

well as by reorganization of global hubs. The topological redistribution of intra- and inter-hemispheric cortical thickness and glucose correlations leads to changes in the relationship between metabolic and structural networks, as revealed by a local decrease and a global increase of F-S coupling. All together, these results show that AD cerebral lesions target the core elements of cortical networks without completely destroying their modular architecture and hierarchical organization. Further investigations are needed to establish those mechanisms that are behind specific topological changes in cortical networks during AD progression in order to anticipate network dysfunctions at the earliest possible stage of neurodegeneration.

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